

D8.8 Public Communication Materials II

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0.3	18/10/2021	Jaume Altesa (ALSTOM)	Revision
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Executive Summary

This deliverable details the communications activities done during M1-M35 including, among others, the development of a corporate visual identity manual, audio-visual promotional materials designed, social media activity, media relations, popularised publications and newsletters.

Table of Contents

REVISION HISTORY	2
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	2
LIST OF FIGURES	4
TERMINOLOGY AND ACRONYMS	5
1. COMMUNICATION PLAN	6
2. COMMUNICATION TOOLS AND MATERIALS	6
2.1 Corporate visual identity	6
2.2 Promotional materials	6
2.3 Website	7
2.4 Social Media	14
2.4.1 <i>Twitter</i>	14
2.4.2 <i>YouTube</i>	14
2.4.3 <i>Partners' social media</i>	15
2.5 Press releases	17
2.6 Popularised publications	18
2.7 Videos	19
2.1.1 <i>Industrial scenarios</i>	19
2.1.2 <i>General video</i>	20
2.1.3 <i>Video quotes</i>	21
2.1.4 <i>Research outputs and modules demonstrations</i>	21
2.8 Newsletter	22
3. KPIS COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES	23
4. ANNEX	25
4.1 List of articles published in online and print media outlets	25

List of Figures

Figure 1: View of part of Sharework flyer.....	6
Figure 2: Sharework rollups.....	7
Figure 3: View of project materials page on SHAREWORK website.....	7
Figure 4: SEAT use-case page.....	8
Figure 5: View of cluster page.....	9
Figure 6: Deliverables pages. It gives access to the abstract of confidential papers and to public deliverables.....	10
Figure 7: Scientific production page.....	10
Figure 8: View of blog page.....	11
Figure 9: View of events' page categorised by conferences, congresses/exhibitions, joint actions with other projects, project meetings & workshops.....	12
Figure 10: Visitors' country of origin by number of visits.....	13
Figure 11: Visitor Map.....	13
Figure 12: View of new cookies banner.....	13
Figure 13: View of Sharework Twitter account.....	14
Figure 14: View of Sharework YouTube Channel.....	15
Figure 15: YouTube analytics.....	15
Figure 16: Examples of some social media posts published by partners featuring Sharework.....	16
Figure 17: View of industrial demonstrators videos.....	20
Figure 18: View of Sharework animated video.....	20
Figure 19: Some examples of partners quote videos.....	21
Figure 20: Videos on Sharework research - modules demonstrations.....	22
Figure 21: Effective Industrial HRC Newsletter sign up form.....	23

Terminology and Acronyms

<i>EC</i>	<i>European Commission</i>
<i>EU</i>	<i>European Union</i>
<i>HRC</i>	<i>Human-Robot Collaboration</i>
<i>VCI</i>	<i>Visual Corporate Identity</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>

1. Communication Plan

Sharework Project communication plan aims at raising awareness on Sharework research, as well as at communicating the benefits that collaborative robotics can bring to the European industrial sector and its employees in terms of safety and ergonomics, among other.

The project's communication plan is based on one hand, on the production of different kind of digital, printed and audio-visual materials that support the project's dissemination activities to the industrial and scientific audience and, on the other hand, the setting up and maintenance of the project's digital channels (social media and website).

For information on target audiences, key messages and channels used *please refer to D8.6 and D8.2.*

2. Communication tools and materials

2.1 Corporate visual identity

Eurecat, as the leader of Communication task developed Shareworks's Corporate Visual Identity, including the project's logo, a Power Point template, Word templates for project activities and a visual identity standards guidebook, defining and outlining how to use identifying elements pertaining to Sharework including logos, colours, fonts, stationery and some marketing and advertising materials. For more information you can refer to **D8.6 Public Communication Materials**.

2.2 Promotional materials

Sharework counts with **set of different promotional materials** an infosheet, leaflet, rollup, a general presentation and poster layout. All materials follow the project visual identity guidelines and are available to all the consortium in an electronic format, so they can be used every time a partner carries out a disseminating activity, such as attending to key conferences and fairs. In addition, all public promotional materials have been made available through the project website (<https://sharework-project.eu/project-materials/>)

During the 3rd year of the project, these materials have been updated to reflect the inclusion of SEAT into the consortium. In addition, new versions of the project rollups and general presentation have been produced.

Figure 1: View of part of Sharework flyer

Figure 2: Sharework rollups

PROJECT MATERIALS

See below all dissemination materials available about the project, including, brochures, infosheets, rollups and a general presentation.

SHAREWORK - TRIFOLD 1 file(s) 1 MB	DOWNLOAD
SHAREWORK - ROLLUP 1 file(s) 3 MB	DOWNLOAD
SHAREWORK - INFOSHEET 1 file(s) 304 KB	DOWNLOAD
SHAREWORK - GENERAL PRESENTATION 1 file(s) 616 KB	DOWNLOAD

Figure 3: View of project materials page on SHAREWORK website

2.3 Website

EUT has maintained the **SHAREWORK project website** (www.SHAREWORK-project.eu), launched in January 2019, with the support of all partners. The website is the anchor of all communication and dissemination activities, displaying the project's basic information, objectives, industrial scenarios and benefits, as well as all dissemination activities and project results.

The website has been regularly updated with dissemination activities. Updates done since the last report include:

- **Substitution of NISSAN use-case page for SEAT's:** <https://sharework-project.eu/automotive-industrial-scenario-seat/>

AUTOMOTIVE INDUSTRIAL SCENARIO SEAT, S.A. Home / Automotive Industrial Scenario SEAT, S.A.

SEAT S.A - OPERATOR COLLABORATIVE SUPPORT ON ASSEMBLING/DISASSEMBLING CAR BODY HEAVY PARTS

SEAT, S.A. is the only company that designs, develops, manufactures and markets cars in Spain. A member of the Volkswagen Group, the multinational has its headquarters in Martorell (Barcelona), sells vehicles under the CUPRA and SEAT brands.

The company employs over 15,000 professionals and has three production centres – Barcelona, El Prat de Llobregat and Martorell. The paint shop of the company, located in Martorell, will act as one of the Sharework project industrial scenarios to demonstrate the effectiveness of industrial collaborative robotics to support operators while assembling and disassembling automotive body parts.

CURRENT SCENARIO

SEAT S.A paint shop regularly receives, from the end of the production line, requests for car parts of various models and colours to replace damaged parts, such as doors or hoods. When this happens, the paint shop asks the body shop for the required parts to be painted.

The pieces arriving to the paint shop are skid-mounted, which are transported by operators to dedicated shelves using a small trolley, as some parts can weight up to 18kg. After this, operators need to assemble the parts to be painted to chassis easels using the trolley to move the parts closely by holding them manually. Once painted, operators need to carefully disassemble the painted parts and transport them to the end of production line to satisfy the demand.

SHAREWORK SCENARIO

AUTOMATISATION OF TRANSPORTATION OF AUTOMOTIVE PIECES AND OPERATORS SUPPORT DURING ASSEMBLY/DISASSEMBLY PROCESSES

Within Sharework project, the transportation of pieces to the paint shop and within it will be redesigned and automatized with the integration of a high payload robot that will carry, position and hold the car pieces while the operator carries the assembly and disassembly tasks needed before and after the painting process.

The main challenges to be solved in Sharework scenario will be to ensure a safe human-robot collaboration and integrate numerous sensors in the environment to provide the robot with the necessary knowledge to be able to detect workers and obstacles, as well as to adjust the trajectory accordingly. Operators would be able to interact with the robot through the Human-Robot interfaces developed in the project, using a tablet to indicate the robot which parts to be mounted and a hand-guiding mechanism that will let them manually guide the robot.

Through the Sharework project, SEAT S.A., a major automotive manufacturer, in collaboration by LMS as technology coach, will ensure a successful integration of Sharework modules and technologies into the paint shop.

EXPECTED BENEFITS

DECREASE THE NON-VALUE ADDED OF THE OPERATION

INCREASE PRODUCTIVITY

REDUCE WORKERS' PHYSICAL FATIGUE

Figure 4: SEAT use-case page

- **Creation of a page with information on the Effective Industrial Human-Robot Collaboration Cluster:** <https://sharework-project.eu/automotive-industrial-scenario-seat/>

EFFECTIVE INDUSTRIAL HUMAN-ROBOT COLLABORATION CLUSTER

The [Sharework project](#) is part of the **Effective Industrial-Human Collaboration Cluster**, which aims at bringing together independent EU-funded R&D projects on collaborative robotics to jointly address the technical scope areas within the context of “*Transforming European Industry*” and more specifically “*Effective Industrial Human-Robot Collaboration*” (DT-FOF-02-2018) and related topics. Via the cluster, the participating projects may expand their impact beyond the project level, while contributing to the dissemination of state-of-the-art research and developments to ensure an effective industrial flexible production that allows humans and robots to coexist and share production tasks.

The *Effective Industrial-Human Collaboration Cluster’s* project coordinators and dissemination managers trust that together, they will boost awareness regarding the research outcomes and promote technology transfer with relevant stakeholders, such as academia and industry, for a smooth integration of human-robot collaboration into industrial environments in an effective and safe manner.

The **Effective Industrial-Human Collaboration Cluster** is comprised of [THOMAS](#), [ROSSINI](#), [HR-Recycler](#), [COLLABORATE](#), [SHERLOCK](#) and [Sharework](#).

CLUSTER OBJECTIVES

- 1 EXPLORING SYNERGIES BETWEEN CLUSTER PROJECTS FOR COMMON DISSEMINATION IN EXTERNAL EVENTS (WORKSHOPS, CONFERENCES, ETC.)
- 2 COLLABORATION IN ORGANISING PROJECT EVENTS ON SPECIFIC TOPICS RELATED TO COLLABORATIVE ROBOTICS
- 3 SHARING THE LATEST NEWS AND ADVANCES ON COLLABORATIVE ROBOTICS AND HUMAN-ROBOT COLLABORATION FROM EUROPEAN RESEARCH INSTITUTIONS AND CLUSTER PROJECTS
- 4 MAXIMISING DISSEMINATION VIA COMBINING EFFORTS FOR JOINT PUBLICATIONS IN JOURNALS AND MAGAZINES, AS WELL AS CREATING DEDICATED MATERIAL AT CLUSTER LEVEL

NEWSLETTERS

1 #1 ISSUE - OCTOBER 2021

This is the first newsletter of the HRC cluster, which aims to disseminate state-of-the-art research and developments on collaborative robotics to ensure an effective industrial flexible production that allows humans and robots to coexist and share production tasks. In this issue, you will be able to find about what is the Effective Industrial Human-Robot Collaboration Cluster, Cluster projects’ updates, scientific publications published and forthcoming events.

[READ THE NEWSLETTER](#)

CLUSTER PROJECTS

THOMAS – Mobile dual arm robotic workers with embedded cognition for hybrid and dynamically reconfigurable manufacturing systems

The project aims to create a dynamically reconfigurable shopfloor utilizing autonomous, mobile dual arm workers. These “workers” are able to perceive their environment and, through reasoning, cooperate with each other and with other production resources, including human operators.

www.thomas-project.eu

COLLABORATE – Co-production cell performing human-robot collaborative assembly

This project aims to equip robots with collaborative skills so that they can learn from the human and become valuable assistants for assembly operations, in an effective and safe manner.

www.collaborate-project.eu

Figure 5: View of cluster page

- **Creation of results pages, giving access to public materials:**
 - o Audiovisual materials (<https://sharework-project.eu/audiovisual-materials/>)
 - o Scientific papers (<https://sharework-project.eu/scientific-production/>)
 - o Media impact (<https://sharework-project.eu/media>)
 - o Deliverables (<https://sharework-project.eu/deliverables>)
 - o Project materials (<https://sharework-project.eu/project-materials/>)

Home / Scientific production

SCIENTIFIC PRODUCTION

SCIENTIFIC PRODUCTION

In this page you will be able to find the scientific publications related to Sharework project published by partners

COMPOSABLE ENERGY POLICIES FOR REACTIVE MOTION GENERATION AND REINFORCEMENT LEARNING

Proceedings of Robotics Science and Systems Conference Julen Urain; Puze Liu; Carlo D'Eramo; Jan Peters (TU Darmstadt); Anqui Li (University of Washington) Abstract Reactive motion generation problems are usually solved by computing actions as a sum of policies. However, these policies are independent of each other and thus, they can have conflicting behaviors when summing...

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SIMPLIFYING THE A.I. PLANNING MODELING FOR HUMAN-ROBOT COLLABORATION

Proceedings of the 30th IEEE International virtual Conference on Robot & Human Interactive Communication (RO-MAN 2021) Elisa Foderaro; Amedeo Cesta; Alessandro Umbrico; Andrea Orlandini (Institute of Cognitive Science and Technology, National Research Council of Italy) Abstract For an effective deployment in manufacturing, Collaborative Robots should be capable of adapting their behavior to the state of the environment...

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MODULAR SYSTEM DESIGN APPROACH FOR ONLINE ERGONOMICS ASSESSMENT IN AGILE PRODUCTION ENVIRONMENT

Proceedings of the 30th IEEE International virtual Conference on Robot & Human Interactive Communication (RO-MAN 2021) Paul Eichler; Aquid Rashid; Ibrahim Al Nasser; Jayanto Halim; Mohamad Bdiwi (Fraunhofer IWU) Abstract Shorter product lifecycles, mass individualization and agile concepts for lot size1 require more flexible production. Constant challenges may result in optimized processes. However, optimization effects not...

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ANYTIME INFORMED PATH RE-PLANNING AND OPTIMIZATION FOR HUMAN-ROBOT COLLABORATION

Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Robot and Human Interactive Communication (IEEE ROMAN) (August 2021) Cesare Tonola (University of Brescia); Marco Faroni, Nicola Pedrocchi (CNR-STIMA) and Manuel Beschi (University of Brescia, CNR-STIMA) Abstract Robots working in proximity of humans often need to change their motion to avoid collisions and interference with the operators. This...

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A TOOL TO MODEL TASK PLANNING DOMAIN FOR HUMAN-ROBOT

CASE STUDY: AI TASK PLANNING SETUP FOR AN

AN ACTION INTERFACE MANAGER FOR ROSPLAN

Figure 7: Scientific production page

PROJECT DELIVERABLES

WP1 - SYSTEM CONCEPTUALIZATION, USE CASE DEFINITION AND MODELLING

D1.1 USE CASES DEFINITION, SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS AND KPIS DEFINITION - ABSTRACT

1 file(s) 344 KB

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D1.2 ROBOTIC SYSTEM SPECIFICATION - DESIGN OF THE SHAREWORK FRAMEWORK - FULL PAPER

1 file(s) 5 MB

DOWNLOAD

D1.3 SIMULATION SCENARIOS AND PRELIMINARY KPIS ASSESSMENT I - ABSTRACT

1 file(s) 219 KB

DOWNLOAD

Figure 6: Deliverables pages. It gives access to the abstract of confidential papers and to public deliverables

- **21 blog posts have been published in the project's blog (<https://sharework-project.eu/news/>)**

Figure 8: View of blog page

- **Update to the events page** (42 articles on events participated / organized have been written since the beginning of the project)

PAST EVENTS

View all Conferences Congresses & Exhibitions Joint actions with other projects Project meetings Workshops

SHAREWORK-RESEARCH PRESENTED AT TAILOR PROJECT CONFERENCE AND SUMMER SCHOOL
September 24, 2021
Sharework project research has been presented during the TAILOR project (H2020 ICT-48) conference (September 21st -22nd) and summer school (September 24th). TAILOR conference gathered the scientific community online to discuss scientific progress. The conference included a presentation on AI planning modelling...
[Read more >](#)

MCM PARTNERS DISTRIBUTE NEW SHAREWORK MATERIALS AT GLOBAL INDUSTRIE 2021
September 14, 2021
Sharework project partner Machining Centers Manufacturing (MCM) participated to the Global Industrie Exhibition which has been celebrated from 6th – 9th of September in the EUREXPO Lyon, France. Partners from MCM, which counted with their own stand, distributed new Sharework flyers...
[Read more >](#)

SHAREWORK PROJECT TAKES PART IN THE ICAPS CONFERENCE 2021
September 7, 2021
Sharework project has been represented during the International Conference on Automated Planning and Scheduling (ICAPS), an international forum aimed at exchanging news and research results on theory applications of intelligent and automated planning and scheduling technology, which has been celebrated...
[Read more >](#)

Figure 9: View of events' page categorised by conferences, congresses/exhibitions, joint actions with other projects, project meetings & workshops

The SHAREWORK website has **Matomo installed** in the platform's back end to monitor all the traffic and obtain, every month, reports about the site's performance. Since its launch in M3, the website has received **8,266 visits, 20,034 page viewed** coming from **5,761 users** (Analytics from June 2019 to 30th September 2021).

As for **geographical and device traffic distribution**, most of the visits from M3-M36 have come from **Spain** and followed by Italy, Germany and France (denoting partners efforts in disseminating the project in their countries). The picture seems relevant also to show that Sharework has impacted beyond EU borders. Concerning devices, most of the sessions have been established through desktop devices.

COUNTRY	VISITS
Spain	2,337
Italy	1,498
Germany	703
United States	557
France	516
Greece	302
China	229
United Kingdom	200
India	188
Belgium	113

Figure 11: Visitor Map

Figure 10: Visitors' country of origin by number of visits

The website has been adapted to the latest directives published by the Spanish Data Protection Agency (AEPD) in July 2020, which came into force on October 31st, 2020 with the purpose to align the cookies installation with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) consent requirements. The latest version of the AEPD "Guidelines on the Use of Cookies", compared with the previous one, specifies that the consent must be granted by clearly accepting the cookies or carrying out similar actions to click "I accept". In that sense, browsing the website or the use the scroll bar cannot be construed as an affirmative action, nor the use of cookie walls that do not provide an alternative to the consent.

Figure 12: View of new cookies banner

In order to comply with the new AEPD directives, EUT, as the owner of the Sharework website, has installed a cookies banner allowing the user to decide on which non-necessary cookies to install. By complying with the novel regulation, web analytics will only be tracked for users accepting this type of cookies, which may result in losing some statistics on the number of web visits, page viewed or number of users.

2.4 Social Media

Eurecat manages SHAREWORK’s social media accounts and their contents described hereinafter. SHAREWORK project with a **Twitter Channel**, [@SHAREWORK_EU](https://twitter.com/SHAREWORK_EU), and of a **YouTube channel**. On the other hand, **partners contribute spreading the word on their corporate and personal Social Media channels**, including accounts in Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn or Instagram.

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The project coordinator is responsible of notifying the European Commission about possible content of interest to be published through its official social media channels.

2.4.1 Twitter

Figure 13: View of Sharework Twitter account

SHAREWORK ’s main objective on Twitter is to raise awareness on the benefits of cobots and HRC for the industry, as well as promoting the project’s results to key stakeholders and the broader audience. Twitter allows us to reach directly targeted audiences from validated professional accounts.

Twitter is updated weekly with content of project meetings, project videos, blog posts, and research and milestones, as well as third party content on cobots, industrial robotics, industry 4.0 and related projects. For a detailed Social Media Plan see *D8.2 Dissemination Plan* and *D8.6 Public Communication*

Materials.

From **M1-M35**, SHAREWORK Twitter account has published over **420 tweets**, **+222K impressions** and counts with **+427 active followers**.

2.4.2 YouTube

On M12, a YouTube channel was created to serve as a content repository of all audio-visual content produced during the project. All videos created are being embedded on the project website audiovisual materials page (<https://sharework-project.eu/audiovisual-materials/>) and shared on Twitter for a broader impact.

Figure 14: View of Sharework YouTube Channel

From the creation of the account, Sharework YouTube channel has received **2,000 views**, **10,400 impressions** and **47,6 watch time hours**.

Figure 15: YouTube analytics

2.4.3 Partners' social media

Each partner has also transmitted SHAREWORK news and results through their personal and corporate social media accounts (Twitter, LinkedIn and Facebook), including press releases, notices about events, promotional materials and other contents published on www.sharework-project.eu or in SHAREWORK's twitter account.

Until M35, partners have published **126 posts** (90 on Twitter and 35 on LinkedIn), which account for **over 960 likes** and **270 shares**. See deliverable 8.2 for a detailed list of partner's available accounts for dissemination.

Figure 16: Examples of some social media posts published by partners featuring Sharework

2.5 Press releases

During M1-M35, several **press releases on the project targeting non-specialised stakeholders**. Press releases have been distributed to all partners and translated into several languages.

- **January 2019** - *The SHAREWORK project to create new technology for human-robot collaboration in the industry* <https://SHAREWORK-project.eu/the-SHAREWORK-project-will-create-new-technology-for-human-robot-collaboration-in-the-industry/>
- **December 2019** - Joint press release with other EU projects working on Collaborative Robotics that participated in the Workshop of the Cluster “Future of Industrial Collaborative Robotics”
<https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5bf59e007c9327b9f9aef60a/t/5dee1acb9778c378d7e00d60/1575885515885/HRC+Projects+Joint+Press+Release.pdf>
- **September 2021** – *Sharework collaborative robotics software tested at lab environment* <https://sharework-project.eu/sharework-collaborative-robotics-software-tested-at-lab-environment/>

Eurecat, in collaboration with Nissan, has also produced 3 country-focused press releases mentioning the project:

- **November 2019** – *Nissan starts 45 R+D and Industry 4.0 projects with Eurecat* <https://eurecat.org/nissan-endegara-45-proyectos-innovacio-tecnologica-industria-4-0-eurecat/>
- **March 2020** - *A new system to improve workers’ security and ergonomics* (in Spanish) <https://eurecat.org/es/nuevo-sistema-inteligente-mejorara-seguridad-priorizara-ergonomia-trabajos-con-robots/>
- **March 2020** – *Eurecat shows the potential of the hybridization of digital and industrial technologies* (in Spanish) <https://eurecat.org/eurecat-mostra-potencial-hibridacio-tecnologias-digitals-industrials/>

Articles and press releases have had a great impact on online and print media. A clipping study covering the project period shows that currently up to **37 articles online media**, **5 articles in print media** and **1 TV piece featuring Sharework** has been produced. *For a complete list of media impacts see Annex.*

A clipping study covering the project period shows that media impact accounts for a total audience of more than 80M which translates on an Economic Value of 478K€ (value equivalent to the press impact).

2.6 Popularised publications

SHAREWORK partners have communicated the project results extensively with popularised publications such as blog posts or press releases published on [SHAREWORK project Blog](#) or partners' websites.

From M1-M35, **22 publications have been published in SHAREWORK blog:**

- **RWTH (October 2021)** - [Task Planning coordinates the actions of mobile manipulators, such as humans and robots](#)
- **STAM (October 2021)** - [Integration of Goizper mock-up at STAM laboratory](#)
- **GOIZPER (October 2021)** - [Boosting productivity and operators' health](#)
- **TUDA (September 2021)** - [Key factor skill composition: which are the structured models to represent human and robot motions](#)
- **EUT (September 2021)** - [Human-tracking, the cornerstone of human-robot collaboration](#)
- **MCM (April 2021)** - [Collaborative automation: a key enabling technology to move from automation islands to integrated and reactive shop floors](#)
- **CEMBRE (April 2021)** - [Sharework collaborative robotics logistic station to be installed at CEMBRE shop floor](#)
- **STRANE (February 2021)** - [From acceptance to sustainable relationship: how can user-centered design facilitate long-term human-robot collaboration](#)
- **LMS (December 2020)** - [Bringing humans and robots closer with a novel interface based on state-of-the-art augmented reality on IoT](#)
- **INTRA (July 2020)** - [Robotics software architecture: architecture and integration of software systems in robotics](#)
- **CEMBRE (May 2020)** - [CEMBRE and the SHAREWORK project: a story on collaborative robots' deployment in flexible manufacturing assembly areas](#)
- **GOIZPER (May 2020)** - [Travelling to Goizper 4.0 with collaborative robotics on board](#)
- **STAM (May 2020)** - [Robotics into handwork manufacturing: the figure of the technology coach for leading an effective and smooth implementation](#)
- **TUDA (February 2020)** - [Key factor movement primitives: how can we make a robot learn from humans?](#)
- **FRAUNHOFER (February 2020)** - [FPGA-based parallelisation combines with 3D zone-based robot control for safe and effective human robot interaction](#)
- **RWTH (February 2020)** - [Key factor computer vision: the role of smart cognition systems in Industry 4.0](#)
- **MCM (January 2020)** - [Human-centred manufacturing for the design of new social sustainable workplaces](#)
- **EUT (December 2019)** - [7 European Projects on Collaborative Robotics You Must Know About](#)
- **EUT (November 2019)** - [NISSAN and the SHAREWORK project: from Intelligent Mobility to Smart Manufacturing](#)
- **STRANE (July 2019)** - [How SHAREWORK paves the way for rich interactions between industry and research in social sciences](#)
- **EUT (June 2019)** - [Collaborative Robotics is the new industrial paradigm](#)
- **EUT (January 2019)** - [The SHAREWORK project will create new technology for human-robot collaboration in the industry](#)

On the other hand, partners published on SHAREWORK activities in the following blogs posts published in their corporate and professional websites:

- **LMS (May 2020)** - [How to setup a ROS Java System in Windows: Setting up a plain ROS Java system that can run in Windows or Linux with no ROS installation](#)
Article created while ROS Java was proven during LMS activities within SHAREWORK project.
- **RWTH (Oct 2020)** – [Camera calibration in SHAREWORK project](#)
Description of the camera-based methods for the localisation of objects in the workspace.
- **GOIZPER (Nov 2020)** – [Goizper participation to SHAREWORK project](#)
Description of Goizper participation to the project and case study
- **EUT (Feb 2019)** - [Safe and effective human-robot cooperation towards a better competitiveness on current automated lack manufacturing processes](#)

2.7 Videos

SHAREWORK partners have produced **21 videos**, including a general video, 9 video quotes with partners, videos on research outputs and modules presentations and industrial scenarios videos.

2.1.1 Industrial scenarios

Partners have produced a series of audio-visual materials on each of the industrial scenarios (ALSTOM, SEAT, GOIZPER and CEMBRE) to be published and shared from all project communication channels (website, social media) and partners' corporate channels.

The videos aim to explain each industrial case briefly, how Sharework technology will be implemented in their assembly or subassembly lines and the benefits of implementing Sharework to their production line. The videos combine images of each industrial scenario and some quotes from each company representatives.

As requested by Spanish partners, the videos for ALSTOM and GOIZPER use were translated into Spanish. All videos have subtitles to be able to follow the explanations from company representatives easily.

Videos produced:

- [CEMBRE - Human-Robot Collaboration at the load/unload stations of logistic manufacturing systems](#)
- [GOIZPER industrial scenario - HRC for operators' assistance on intermittent indexing units' assembly](#)
- [ALSTOM industrial scenario – Human-Robot Collaboration to improve trains' manufacturing processes](#)

- SEAT Industrial Scenario - Human-Robot Collaboration during Door Assembly Into the Vehicle

Figure 17: View of industrial demonstrators videos

2.1.2 General video

Informative conceptual video about the project in motion graphics describing the project's main objectives and expected outputs. In order to compensate the predominance of male characters in other videos produced, a female character was used.

Figure 18: View of Sharework animated video

2.1.3 Video quotes

- **9 video quotes with partners on specific topics:**

- [What is cognitive robotics \(EUT\)](#)
- [The use of motion primitives to understand human gestures \(TUDA\)](#)
- [Understanding human motions and tasks in a collaborative workspace \(EUT\)](#)
- [Collaborative robotics system in the era of cybersecurity \(INTRA\)](#)
- [Collaborative robotics on task and motion planning \(CNR\)](#)
- [New technology acceptance at the workplace \(STRANE\)](#)
- [Process and challenges of implementing new robotic systems \(STAM\)](#)
- [Collaborative automation \(MCM\)](#)
- [Sharework cognition system \(RWTH\)](#)

Figure 19: Some examples of partners quote videos

2.1.4 Research outputs and modules demonstrations

- [Demonstration of Sharework human-robot interface](#)
- [Screw detection for Goizper Use Case](#)
- [Demonstration of Sharework local safety system](#)
- [Automated task planning for Human-Robot teaming](#)
- [Demonstration of Sharework human awareness in robot motion planning](#)

Figure 20: Videos on Sharework research - modules demonstrations

2.8 Newsletter

Direct dissemination has been established through direct mailing in order to increase the impact of our communication and dissemination activities. In that regard, Sharework, represented by EUT, has established a collaboration with THOMAS, ROSSINI, HR-Recycler, COLLABORATE, SHERLOCK projects to produce a jointly newsletter on the latest news and advances on collaborative robotics and human-robot collaboration from the six Horizon 2020 funded projects.

This newsletter to be issued at least twice a year and will compile state-of-the-art developments towards achieving a safe and effective HRC in the form of blog posts, papers and audio-visual materials.

To this end, a registration form was prepared, which was **published on the website homepage and promoted via the projects' social media channels**. The signup form complies with GDPR, linking to the newsletter privacy policy and informing the user about its right to cancel the subscription at any moment.

Effective Industrial Human-Robot Collaboration Newsletter

Subscribe now to receive in your inbox the Effective Industrial Human-Robot Collaboration Cluster newsletter on the latest news and advances on collaborative robotics and human-robot collaboration from European research institutions and six Horizon 2020 funded projects: THOMAS, ROSSINI, HR-Recycler, COLLABORATE, SHERLOCK and Sharework.

This newsletter will be issued twice a year and will compile state-of-the-art developments towards achieving a safe and effective HRC in the form of blog posts, papers and audiovisual materials.

First Name

Last Name

Email Address

I want to subscribe to (according to the privacy):

The Effective Industrial Human-Robot Collaboration Newsletter

Privacy Policy Information

We will use the information you provide on this form to send you the "Effective Industrial Human-Robot Collaboration Newsletter" biyearly in your inbox according to the Privacy Information that you may find it below.

I have read and I accept the privacy policy

Please, read the [Privacy Information](#) before submit your Subscription to the Effective Industrial Human-Robot Collaboration Newsletter, where you may find the information about your personal data processing.

We use Mailchimp as our marketing platform. By clicking below to subscribe, you acknowledge that your information will be transferred to Mailchimp for processing. [Learn more about Mailchimp's privacy practices here.](#)

Though the newsletter, Sharework and sister-project aim at reaching the main stakeholders groups defined for exploitation, specially the scientific and academic community and industrial community, who may become potential customers of the collaborative robotics solutions being developed.

EUT has used [Mailchimp](#) as the email platform used for the newsletter design, sending and stats monitoring. **In October 2021 a first newsletter issue has been produced** including news on what is the Effective Industrial Human-Robot Collaboration Cluster, Cluster projects' updates, scientific publications published and forthcoming events (*read the first issue [here](#)*).

Newsletter analytics, such as open rate or click through rate, will be extracted through Mailchimp. Statistics will be checked 3 days after sending the newsletter and will be analysed in order to see which articles worked best and be able to improve the newsletter impact in the following issues.

Figure 21: Effective Industrial HRC Newsletter sign up form

3. KPIs Communication activities

Strategy	Indicator	Means of verification	M1- M35 (Nov 2018 - Sept 2021)	Target by the end of the project
Website	Number of web visits	Matomo Analytics	8,266	>4,500
	Number pages viewed		20,034	>10,000
	Number actions / session		2,8	>1,5
	Avg. session time		3,23 min	>1,50min
Social Media (Twitter)	Number Followers	Twitter Analytics	427	>150
	Number Tweets		412	>200
	Twitter Impressions		221,181	>50,000

	Mentions		>150	>20
Social Media (partners' accounts)	Number posts	Monthly follow up (quantitative)	126	>20
	Number Likes		960	>50
	Number Shares / Retweets		270	>10
Press Releases	Number of press releases	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	6	>8

4. ANNEX

4.1 List of articles published in online and print media outlets

Date	Media	Title	Type	Audience	Economic Value	Link
22/04/20	infoPLC.net	#HM20 - Soluciones de Robótica II	Online	11169	67,01	Link
15/03/20	La Razón -Innovadores	ESCAPARATE DE IDEAS	Print	229000	2384,71	Link
13/03/20	Automatica e instrumentacion	La automoción marca el camino de la fábrica conectada	Online	3602	7,2	Link
11/03/20	TecnoNews	Impulsar el trabajo conjunto entre operarios y robots	Online	1000	1	Link
06/03/20	Factoria del Futuro	Un sistema inteligente priorizará la ergonomía de los trabajos con robots	Online	1000	1	Link
06/03/20	InterEmpresas Net	Un nuevo sistema inteligente mejorará la seguridad y priorizará la ergonomía de los trabajos con robots	Online	64343	308,84	Link
05/03/20	Noticias de Gipuzkoa	Goizper participa en un proyecto de interacción entre robots y empleados	Online	NA	NA	Link
04/03/20	elconfidencial.com	Prueban un nuevo sistema inteligente que mejora los trabajos con robots	Online	974769	4971,32	Link
04/03/20	ABC.es	Prueban un nuevo sistema inteligente que mejora los trabajos con robots	Online	1383153	8298,92	Link
04/03/20	Mundoplast.com	Eurecat participa en Advanced Factories 2020	Online	1000	1	Link
04/03/20	La Vanguardia	Prueban un nuevo sistema inteligente que mejora los trabajos con robots	Online	1527887	7792,22	Link
03/03/20	Factoria del Futuro	Eurecat muestra la hibridación de las tecnologías digitales e industriales	Online	1000	1	Link
01/02/20	Automática e Instrumentación	LA AUTOMOCIÓN MARCA EL CAMINO DE LA FÁBRICA CONECTADA	Print	19608	18484,23	Link
19/11/19	Mundoplast.com	Nissan y Eurecat colaboran en innovación tecnológica e industria 4.0	Online	93	0,19	Link
13/11/19	Tool-Maker.net	Nissan emprenderá 45 proyectos de innovación tecnológica e industria 4.0 con Eurecat	Online	278	1,11	Link
13/11/19	TecnoNews	Nissan emprenderá 45 proyectos de innovación tecnológica con Eurecat	Online	186	0,37	Link
08/11/19	Smart-Lighting.es	Nissan emprenderá 45 proyectos de digitalización e industria 4.0 en sus plantas de producción	Online	616	1,23	Link
06/11/19	Factoría del Futuro	Nissan emprenderá 45 proyectos de industria 4.0 de la mano de Eurecat	Online	1000	n/d	Link
05/11/19	Redes Telecoms	Digitalización e Industria 4.0 en Nissan	Online	155	0,31	Link
05/11/19	VilaWeb	Nissan i Eurecat emprendran 45 projectes d'innovació tecnològica i indústria 4.0	Online	82536	321,89	Link

05/11/19	La República	Nissan i Eurecat emprendran 45 projectes d'innovació tecnològica i indústria 4.0	Online	12345	37,04	Link
05/11/19	Europa Press	Nissan y Eurecat colaborarán en 45 proyectos tecnológicos hasta 2022	Online	271412	1954,17	Link
05/11/19	Gente Digital	Nissan y Eurecat colaborarán en 45 proyectos tecnológicos hasta 2022	Online	6171	24,69	Link
05/11/19	Actualitat Diària	Nissan i Eurecat uneixen els seus sinergías en 45 projectes d'innovació tecnològica fins a 2022	Online	155	0,31	Link
05/11/19	CastellonInformacion.com	Nissan y Eurecat unen sus sinergías en 45 proyectos de innovación tecnológica hasta 2022	Online	6171	12,34	Link
05/11/19	Motor Tenerife	Nissan emprenderá 45 proyectos de innovación tecnológica e industria 4.0 con Eurecat	Online	213	0,43	Link
05/11/19	InterEmpresas Net	Nissan emprenderá 45 proyectos de innovación tecnológica e Industria 4.0 con Eurecat	Online	86034	387,15	Link
05/11/19	Metalindustria	Nissan emprenderá 45 proyectos de innovación tecnológica e industria 4.0 con Eurecat	Online	null	n/d	Link
05/11/19	MSN Spain	Nissan y Eurecat colaborarán en 45 proyectos tecnológicos hasta 2022	Online	34689536	409336,51	Link
01/11/19	Técnica y Tecnología para la Automoción	NISSAN EMPRENDERÁ 45 PROYECTOS DE INNOVACIÓN TECNOLÓGICA E INDUSTRIA 4.0 CON EURECAT	Print	1000	4380	Link
10/10/19	mc mutual	INDUSTRIA 4.0 Y ROBÓTICA COLABORATIVA. EL FUTURO YA ESTÁ AQUÍ	Online	1232	2,46	Link
23/07/19	El Periodico de Cataluña	Eurecat lidera un proyecto tecnológico para la colaboración hombre-robot	Online	939320	5325,94	Link
18/05/19	Giornale di Brescia	Sharework: la svolta dei robot passa da Cembre	Online	36206	260,69	Link
18/05/19	Brescia TeleTutto	Cembre Sharework	TV	NA	NA	Link
18/05/19	Giornale di Brescia	Sharework: la nuova frontiera dei robot passa da Cembre	Print	Null	Na	Link
31/05/19	La Vanguardia	NUEVO PROYECTO EUROPEO	Print	61500	1362,66	Link
30/01/19	TecnoNews	Proyecto europeo para la colaboración hombre-robot en la industria	Online	309	0,618	Link
28/01/19	InterEmpresas Net	@Eurecat_news Eurecat lidera un proyecto tecnológico europeo para la colaboración hombre-robot en la industria	Online	45910	220,362	Link
27/01/19	Prevencionar	Eurecat lidera un proyecto tecnológico europeo para la colaboración hombre-robot en la industria	Online	10492	40,92	Link
24/01/19	CIC Construcción	Eurecat lidera un proyecto tecnológico europeo para la colaboración hombre-robot en la industria	Online	616	1,232	Link
24/01/19	Tool-Maker.net	Eurecat lidera un proyecto tecnológico europeo para la colaboración hombre-robot en la industria	Online	62	0,124	Link
23/01/19	La Vanguardia	Eurecat lidera un proyecto tecnológico para la colaboración hombre-robot	Online	1544680	9453,441	Link

